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Abstract:

The SSHOC communication strategy is a SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound) and KPI-driven approach to successful community building and stakeholder engagement, design and promotion of the Marketplace, content creation and development of the Communication Toolbox, and social media campaigns. Moreover, experience has demonstrated, amongst many things, that the most important dissemination recommendations and actions should be **Realistic, Implementable, Achievable and Measurable**.

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Executive summary

This project aims to build a Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) as part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by implementing a cloud based-infrastructure to maximize the interconnectedness of existing and new research infrastructures. The goal is to provide a recognisable and accessible environment for data, tools, services and trainings, and to maximise data reuse through Open Science and FAIR principles.

As stated in the Grant Agreement Article 38.1, “the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner”¹. In line with this, this document sets out a strategy for communication, and additionally for dissemination. Both, communication activities as well as dissemination activities contribute fundamentally to the project’s visibility, outreach, and impact. This document will provide guidance to the projects’ partners in order to make the most of their activities. This strategy document outlines the main objectives, target groups, tools, and activities for communication and dissemination of the SSHOC.

The methodological approach in the communications strategy laid out here, the focus of the proposed activities addresses the concepts of inserting research results in the specific policy context in which they are implemented. The approach also aligns with best practices and results of other EOSC implementation projects. This adheres to the goals set out by the European Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation Carlos Moedas, who sets out three major points for the EU research and innovation policy, which are summarised as “**Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World**”².

The SSHOC communication strategy is a SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound) and KPI-driven approach to successful community building and stakeholder engagement, design and promotion of the Marketplace, content creation and development of the Communication Toolbox, and social media campaigns. Moreover, experience has demonstrated, amongst many things, that the most important dissemination recommendations and actions should be **Realistic, Implementable, Achievable and Measurable**.

It ensures extensive interactions between and with ERICs and SSH ESFRI Landmarks, open source communities, policy makers as well as private and industry players active in the pilot domains of Social Science and Economics, Migration & Mobility, Election Studies, Language & Humanities, Culture and Heritage, with content tailored to different professional roles and research cultures. The strategy also aims to support the project policy approach towards the EOSC, showcasing collaboration success stories and topics of common interest, and a go-to plan for the project main sustainable asset, the SSH Open Marketplace.

¹ SSHOC Grant Agreement

² <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/open-innovation-open-science-open-world-vision-europe>

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESS	European Social Survey
EVS	European Values Study
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
GGP	Generations and Gender Programme
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of the present document is to define the strategy and foreseen activities for communication and outreach for SSHOC WP2, “Dissemination, Communication and Impact”. In particular, a drill-down on the stakeholder groups and channels utilised is enclosed.

Owing to the early stage in the project, some of the detailed information around results achieved and communication and dissemination assets related to those is still not available at the time of writing. Therefore, the report is effectively to be considered, for some aspects, a “living document”, which will not be changed in the core structure, but will be updated or expanded (for instance with guidance documents in the Annex).

1.2 Relation to other SSHOC outputs

The SSHOC Overall Communication and Impact Plan is part of the endeavours of WP2 (“Communication, Dissemination and Impact”). Given the cross-cutting theme of the WP, the ideas and guidelines sketched out in this document affect the creation of all content within the project. All organizations involved in the project are expected to contribute to communication, dissemination, and impact. They are kindly asked to follow the communication guidelines which will be provided in this document and through other means (templates, etc.).

While all WPs engage in communication, there is a strong connection to specific WPs which are dedicated to outreach (WP6 “Fostering Communities, Empowering Users & Building Expertise”) and the creation of the project’s infrastructure (WP7 “Creating the SSH Open Marketplace”). Contributors to WP2 participate also in these and other work packages, fostering further interaction and the alignment of activities. Specific actions which are also affected by this plan are:

- SSHOC web platform (WP2)
- Communities engagement (WP2 - WP6)
- SSHOC Open Marketplace (WP7)
- D8.1 Governance and Sustainability Roadmap
- Continuous communication and dissemination of SSHOC’s research and innovation activities (all WPs)

This document does not guide internal project communication - something that is seen to within WP1 in general and in D1.1 (“Project Management Plan”) in specific.

1.3 Structure of the document

The document is organised in three central sections:

- Section 2 defines the project's strategy for communication and dissemination. Objectives, stakeholders, value propositions, and channels are explained in detail.
- The assets available for dissemination and communication arising from the expected project results are described in Section 3.
- Section 4 lays out the Communication and Dissemination plan itself.

2. Strategy

SSHOC is innovative, forward looking and important to different stakeholders. Efficient communication contributes enormously to its success and contributes to maximising the project’s reach. Thus, the main objective of this document is to ensure the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination activities to widely promote the innovation and benefits of SSHOC to targeted stakeholders, maximise visibility, activate end-user communities, disseminate results, and demonstrate impact. It is an overall communication objective that the project's output (prototypes, code, data, etc.) is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Furthermore, the FAIR principles apply for the project's communication, meaning that all communication is conducted in an open and transparent manner. This implies, for instance, that communication strategy documents and anonymized data collected for communication purposes will be shared with external audiences (further elaborated in D1.6 Data Management Plan - DMP).

To ensure coordinated, regular communication of SSHOC, providing opportunity of visibility to all stakeholders, as well as developing an effective exploitation approach, the following strategic elements have been established, in good agreement with the provisions of the grant agreement.

2.1 Objectives

SSHOC aims to provide an open access infrastructure with benefits to different target groups. The intended main impacts are presented in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1: SSHOC OBJECTIVES

To achieve the impact above, WP2 collaborates with all SSHOC partners to:

- Ensure a proper communication and outreach strategy of SSHOC outputs, outreach, and stakeholder engagement and subsequently raise awareness to the scientific, industrial, and SSH communities;
- Promote and support the organisation of EU-wide dissemination of targeted workshops and concertation actions in Europe as well as webinars and training events, especially on data skills and other training opportunities arising from the project;

- Implement and maintain homogeneous design and branding under the SSHOC umbrella of all tools, services, and materials delivered, including communication collaterals, online visuals, and logos to be used in the promotion of the online Marketplace;
- Engage in regular social media activities and with media outlets and journalists, conduct communication via newsletters, press releases, and the like.

2.2 Stakeholders

To maximise impact through collective and individual expertise and networks, the plans for knowledge generated, e.g. deliverables, tools, new products and services are scheduled at specific times during and after the project ends. Users of SSHOC span scholars from the broader SSH domain, data producers, open source communities (developers and users); industry players well beyond the consortium (start-ups, SMEs and large companies); EU-funded projects and a SSH cluster still at their implementation phase (GGP, EVS, WWI, Europeana); public administrations and public services (libraries), thus generating considerable socio-economic impact. Partners have already identified an initial set of targeted users and stakeholders to ensure early onboarding of community members and momentum building, while also taking into account the main EOSC stakeholders as identified by the EOSCpilot project. Figure 2 presents the priority stakeholders for the SSHOC output. The original list of stakeholders as defined in the SSHOC GA, has been changed in light of wanting to introduce a larger audience base. This change has been based on the recommendations introduced by the Open Science Policy Platform³ and partners' insights.

As highlighted already by Ron Dekker (CESSDA Director, SSHOC Coordinator) during the SSHOC Kick-Off March 11 -12 in Utrecht, The Netherlands "Researchers often don't feel they are part of an end-user community". It is therefore important to raise researchers' and other end-users' awareness on the added value of the SSHOC assets for their research and work. This this will be done in discussion and collaboration with the task leaders during the project. For the social sciences, there is a focus on "Migration & Mobility", "Election Studies", and "Culture & Heritage" because those are the topics of the pilot studies which will be carried out as part of the SSHOC project.

³ OSPP-REC – DRAFT recommendations of the Open Science Policy Platform.

FIGURE 2: SSHOC STAKEHOLDERS AND PILOT STUDY FOCI.

2.3 SSHOC value propositions

Collectively, the SSHOC exploitation plan will cover a broad range of sustainable actions from both a commercial and research perspective, including the reuse of assets acquired through ESFRI Landmark initiatives. A series of ready-to-use assets will be part of the SSHOC Joint Exploitation Plan, which will be reported on regularly through WP1. A summary of future SSHOC assets and/or results to be exploited are the following: the vocabulary services, the citation module, the switchboard, MT evaluation kit, the interoperability hub, and as the major exploitation action is the activation of SSHOC Marketplace, which brings very specific benefits to all of the stakeholder groups involved and potentially sustaining business opportunities, as briefly outlined in table 1 below.

TABLE 1: SSHOC value propositions

Stakeholders	Value propositions / Expected SSHOC results
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● solutions and resources for the digital aspects of their research ● SSH datasets, tools, and services like in an app store ● tutorials and training material, user stories ● a self-assessment feature to rate their contribution to research in the Humanities ● new solutions to test to add value to existing SSH primary data collections ● data which is easily repurposed and reusable across disciplines ● more data deposited with less effort ● increased visibility and value of data to the scientific and policy communities ● secure and trusted repositories for storing and accessing SSH data ● an open source software platform, customised to the needs of the European SSH community, sustainable after the end of the action
Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● a common governance model for the project results as part of EOSC ● common policies on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FAIR principles ○ data stewardship and harmonisation ○ quality assessment and impact ● context-driven training
Research Libraries & Archives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● new solutions to test to add value to existing SSH primary data collections ● more data deposited with less effort ● increased visibility and value of data to the scientific and policy communities ● SSH datasets, tools, and services like in an app store ● tutorials and training material, user stories

Universities & Research Performing Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● new solutions to test to add value to existing SSH primary data collections ● data which is easily repurposed and reusable across disciplines ● more data deposited with less effort ● increased visibility and value of data to the scientific and policy communities ● SSH datasets, tools, and services like in an app store ● tutorials and training material, user stories
Policy Making Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● access to national and institutional data that can be made comparable at a European level ● harmonisation effort of domain specific data policies and management of IPRs and ethical issues ● reports on legislative or interoperability issues which affect data handling across geographical and discipline borders
Research Funding Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● access to national and institutional data that can be made comparable at a European level ● harmonisation effort of domain specific data policies and management of IPRs and ethical issues
Private Sector & Industry players	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● business opportunities to exploit the Marketplace services ● domain specific skilled professionals on data stewardships
Civil Society and Citizen Scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● an open source software platform, customised to the needs of the European SSH community, sustainable after the end of the action.

2.4 Channels

SSHOC will use various communication channels leveraging on the project partner networks and will produce a set of tailored communication formats targeting different stakeholder groups. The consortium can count on extensive expertise and experience in creating a communication kit with diverse formats and extend the strong network by reaching out to a broad range of stakeholders, media, professional and social channels. Content will be tailored for different stakeholders. The main channels that will be utilised in SSHOC are visualized in Table 2 together with the affinity of the stakeholder groups to these channels:

TABLE 2: HEATMAP INDICATING STAKEHOLDERS AND THEIR AFFINITY TO SSHOC COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Channel	Assumed affinity of stakeholders to channels							
	Researchers	Research & e-Infrastructures, (EOSC Thematic Clusters)	Research Libraries & Archives	Universities & Research Performing Organisations	Policy-making Organisations	Research Funding Organisations	Private Sector & Industry Players	Civil Society and Citizen Scientists
SSHOC website	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
Social media	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Dark Blue
Events (physical and virtual)	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Light Blue
Traditional media and other channels	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Light Blue	Dark Blue

Figure 3, which has been taken from the description of the strategy delivered by Trust-IT on the pilot project issued by the EC in 2017 – entitled the Common Dissemination Booster, supporting European Commission projects cluster together to disseminate more effectively, describes the communication channels and the other elements at the basis of an effective communication strategy.

ELEMENTS DETERMINING A COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

FIGURE 3: ELEMENTS DETERMINING AN EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY.

2.4 SSHOC website considerations

The SSHOC web platform, sshopencloud.eu, is the unique access point for the SSHOC Marketplace and it will showcase the project's objectives and partners, news, and events.

A preliminary landing page of the website was already up in month 1 at the start date of the project. The first version of SSHOC's website was launched in February 2019 (MS3) providing information about the project and the SSHOC Marketplace. Users could register an account and receive the newsletter. The webpage is planned and structured to ensure visibility and easy access to the technologies and services, as well as innovations mechanisms in data production, use cases and training materials, targeting data producers, data users, and reusers in the SSH disciplines as well as industry players.

The website will also serve as the main repository for all published content and allow access to project deliverables and external resources. It will have specific sections dedicated to events and workshops and it may contain sections to collect user feedback. It will be able to host software repositories developed within SSHOC and it will provide direct access points to the ERICs' websites and other relevant websites, existing catalogues (such as <http://calenda.org>), and virtual labs.

FIGURE 4: FIRST RELEASE OF THE SSHOC PLATFORM IN FEBRUARY 2019.

The SSHOC website will have different iterations during the project’s lifetime aligned with the forthcoming results and defined as Milestones 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7.

Social media and professional networks

Social media is a core element of SSHOC communication, especially to follow ongoing developments and to connect to different stakeholders. SSHOC makes use of social media channels and professional networks such as Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, GitHub, Speakerdeck, Zenodo, and Flickr and thereby builds a stronger and better-connected SSH community.

Additionally, the Marketplace will encompass community interaction via a host of measures: gathering user feedback amongst others via a comment section, ratings and, popularity measures, access to training materials, integration of other related channels, multiple classification schemes, and qualified links to involved actors – persons and institutions who authored, contributed to, funded, or host a given resource.

Events

To maximise impact towards SSHOC stakeholders and in collaboration with relevant WPs, such as WP6, WP2 is promoting and supporting the organisation of EU-wide targeted workshops, coordination meetings, webinars, and training events in collaboration with WP6. There will be events organised by SSHOC, co-branded events of the institutions participating in SSHOC, SSH Community conferences and workshops, in which SSHOC will be present, and “EOSC family” and FAIR-related events. The presence of SSHOC project

partners at events where they will present a session, paper or poster will be mapped in a shared document to plan engagement and promotion effectively.

Examples of large events exclusively organized by SSHOC include the project kick-off, a mid-project SSHOC stakeholder forum, and the SSHOC final conference. Beside these large events, which showcase the project's progress and achievements and engage with a broader range of stakeholders and other European initiatives, there will be a number of smaller SSHOC-dedicated events.

Train-the-trainer workshops, a series of geographically distributed workshops addressing different target audiences (e.g. data producers, data users, data experts, “non-savvy researchers”, librarians, secure data facility professionals, policy makers, civil society), and disciplinary perspectives will be organised.

Traditional media and other channels

Notwithstanding continual usage of web, social media, and visibility at specialised events, SSHOC will also dedicate effort to ensure presence in “traditional media” with the main goal of further expanding outreach, especially to large numbers of Research Centres, Academia, European SMEs and Citizens. A sample is provided below and includes channels with which the SSHOC consortium already has close links.

TABLE 3: SAMPLE OF TRADITIONAL AND OTHER CHANNELS FOR SSHOC

Type of channel	Identified channels
European press/media channels	MyScienceWork, sciDev, Digital Meets Culture, CORDIS Wire & CORDIS News, EC Research and Innovation Press Centre, European Research Journal, EU Observer, Science Direct, EU Agenda & European Agenda, EurActiv, PRLog and PRWeb, DG CNECT/RTD newsletter, The European Journal, Noodles, Europost.
International press/media channels	NUANCE (Newsletter of UbuntuNet Alliance), CONNECT (Magazine from the GEANT Community), CAAST-Net PLUS Magazine, CG Channel, Make, Technology News, DCI, WorldNewsPress.net, Webnuz, New York Social Diary, Before It's News, Sina English, Voices - Sun Times, The Central News Agency, Bizcommunity.com, Copernicus Observer, International innovation
IT, policy and scientific journals	e-IRG, Research EU Magazine, Journal of Web Engineering, Journal on Digital Libraries (IJDL), European Commission
EOSC, ICT and e-Infrastructures	EOSC Portal, EOSC-hub, EUDAT, D4Science, EGI, PRACE

2.5 KPI-driven approach

This plan adopts a SMART approach to its continuous communication activities along the 40-month project life-cycle [specific, measurable (KPI-driven), achievable and realistic (based on identified target groups and channels to reach target groups), timely (matched to project opportunities and results) and timed (clear start and end date)]. KPIs that are relevant for communication and engagement are indicated in the table 4 “SSHOC Communication and Dissemination KPIs”. The roadmap clearly defines a set of macro activities which include more detailed, specific activities that the Consortium will undertake to ensure an effective communication and outreach strategy spanning across a 40-months period.

Evaluation of the communication and dissemination activities will be based on several reference points. Measurable impacts (KPIs) are tracked on a monthly basis through a “Flash Report” monitoring the visibility, engagement, and dissemination potential of online activities in an automated software which extracts, analyses, and visualises the selected KPIs (explained in section 4.7). Additionally, the presentation of papers at scientific conferences and publication of articles in open-access journals by researchers in SSHOC will be monitored. There will be a preliminary report on user communities’ engagement in M24 and a final report on user communities’ engagement in M38. These deliverables will indicate the actions taken to engage stakeholders and the effectiveness of the communication and promotional campaigns. Two iterations are foreseen.

KPI-based Communication Toolbox

A professional and dynamically evolving Communication ToolKit will cover the design and maintenance of the common SSH Open Cloud, including the full R&D and ready-to-market assets within the Marketplace. SSHOC will produce various communication formats tailored to the different stakeholder groups. These formats include practical guides, video clips, webinars, advertising banners, infographics and factsheets to capture trends, newsletters, slide decks, GUIs, brochures, press releases, etc. These form part of the SSHOC communication toolkit as an essential part of the communications and marketing strategy. The strategy is KPI-based and includes joint actions of the SSH ERICs. A set of webinars, especially on data skills including data citation and training materials available from the project, will be organised and broadcasted (and published for later use). The elements, related measures and metrics regarding communication and dissemination actions that the project will undertake to ensure the effectiveness of its outreach and exploitation strategy are stated below in table 4.

TABLE 4: SSHOC COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION KPIS

Communication tool		KPIs (total numbers over 40 months)
Communication Toolbox	Webinars	8 webinars 1000 views >30 registered participants per webinar
	Newsletter	20 newsletters 400 subscribers Opening rate 25% of each newsletter
	Print material	2 roll up banners (1 general, 1 marketplace) 5 brochures (1 general, 1 marketplace, 3 pilot studies)
	Presentation	1 PowerPoint template 1 PowerPoint general information presentations (regularly updated)
	Document templates	1 template for internal and public deliverables 1 template for external communication
	Press releases	6 (launch, marketplace, etc.)
Web presence	Website with Marketplace	800 views/month
	News pieces on website	>40 pieces
Digital community interaction	Twitter	>900 Tweets 30.000 impressions/month
	LinkedIn	>900 LinkedIn Posts 1 LinkedIn article per month
Physical events and local activities	Conferences	3 (Kick-off, mid-project stakeholder forum, final conference) >100 per conference All stakeholder groups should be represented at the mid-project stakeholder forum and the final conference.
Non-scientific publications	EOSC portal magazine and other publications	1 news piece every quarter from M6

3. SSHOC results and assets for dissemination and communication

In following the strategy set out, the dissemination, communication, and engagement efforts will follow a clear process which can be synthesised as follows:

- Identification of a tangible project result;
- Definition of its availability date;
- Agreement of the dissemination and communication assets on the basis of which to develop the stakeholder engagement activities.

Project results are expected as follows:

- SSHOC Marketplace with integrated services
- SSHOC training and training material
- SSHOC pilot studies
- SSHOC governance in the EOSC context.

3.1 SSHOC Marketplace with integrated services

As SSHOC's core project, the SSHOC Marketplace will foster the sharing and reuse of Social Science, Humanities, Art, and Linguistic tools, data and data infrastructures as well as other services. The Marketplace will provide a platform where researchers and other users can easily find project resources. All assets developed in the course of SSHOC, such as data infrastructures, tools, training materials, and the data itself will be made available from the Marketplace. Furthermore, user feedback tools will be implemented. In addition, gap analyses will identify missing tools, which will be subsequently developed, all done in close collaboration with the community.

The Marketplace's success will depend on the usage of its services and on community interaction. Consequently, the Marketplace will be disseminated through every possible channel.

3.2 Training and training material

A comprehensive set of online and offline trainings, workshops, seminars, tutorials, and other training materials will be collected and developed to expand the network of user communities and provide them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and expertise to use and contribute to SSHOC services appropriately, effectively, and efficiently. The physical events and the virtual tutorials, web seminars, and training materials provided through the Marketplace will facilitate and increase the use of the Marketplace and its services. Furthermore, an international and cross-disciplinary trainer network will be built to spread expertise and training resources.

To reach a broad community, comprehensive communication is essential to increase participation and community engagement in physical and virtual trainings and workshops. A strategic document addressing community engagement will be provided by WP6.

3.3 Pilot studies

Three pilot studies with different topics from different (inter-)disciplines will be conducted, applying the Open Science and FAIR principles promoted by SSHOC and using the methods, tools, and services provided by the Marketplace. On the one hand, the participating research groups will identify the problems and obstacles in using SSHOC resources to improve the usability of the Marketplace. On the other hand, these studies should also serve as best practice examples and role models for other studies. It is therefore important to communicate both the experiences and successes gained from conducting the pilot studies with a wide variety of researchers. In addition, however, the tools developed in the course of the studies and the data obtained will be available for reuse at the Marketplace. Therefore, the results, data, and tools of these studies should be widely disseminated and exploited.

3.4 SSHOC network and governance in the EOSC context

Another important asset of the SSHOC project is the network of people and institutions that is being created through the project. SSHOC connects very different people and institutions from the Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe. This is a big achievement in itself, given the different needs of researchers, research infrastructures and other stakeholders from these domains. SSHOC also creates and shapes the SSH part of the European Open Science Cloud. It coordinates with the Cluster projects from other disciplines and is also heavily involved in the exchange with policy makers, industry, and public administration on different levels in Europe.

SSHOC is one of the five European Union H2020 Programme “INFRA-EOSC-2018” recently funded cluster projects (together with [ENVRI-FAIR](#), [PANOSC](#), [ESCAPE](#), EOSC-LIFE) that will leverage and interconnect existing and new infrastructures from the SSH ERICs and foster interdisciplinary research and collaboration. SSHOC will set up an appropriate governance model for the SSH part of the EOSC, taking into account the specificities of different sub-domains of the Social Sciences and Humanities. A task force will be set up with EOSC-hub project to exchange and harmonise views on common themes and existing contacts with other European and international organisations operating in and around the EOSC space will be invited to engage in the process. Furthermore, several SSHOC project partners are directly involved in the EOSC implementation projects and bodies such as EOSC Pilot, EOSC Portal, EOSC Secretariat and EOSC Board which will enable close collaboration with the wider EOSC context.

4. Communication and dissemination plan

To support its goals and generate impact, SSHOC implements a 40-month communication strategy aimed at supporting the dissemination and exploitation goals and targets of the project, coordinated under WP2 – Communication, Dissemination and Impact, drawing on the extensive know-how, experience, and network within and of the SSHOC consortium.

Throughout the duration of the project, all SSHOC partners contribute to community development and stakeholder engagement on a continuous basis as part of the project’s communication plan. Having an effective communication plan is key to paving the way to dissemination and exploitation of results, to which all partners have committed according to availability dates and beyond the project lifecycle.

Assets to support these goals include an already strong community of all SSH ESFRI Landmarks and projects (CESSDA, ESS, DARIAH, CLARIN and SHARE), relevant international SSH data infrastructures and the Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER), especially through LIBER’s SSH-relevant Working Groups. Moreover, SSHOC benefits from close connections with the EOSC Executive Board, EOSC secretariat and both the EOSChub and EOSC portal projects. The various stakeholder groups defined in table 1 will be targeted by a number of engagement activities and campaigns aimed at awareness-raising and recruiting end users.

4.1 Starting point: the SSHOC community

SSHOC’s community builds on an extensive network of European Research Infrastructure Consortia and Landmarks in the Social Sciences and Humanities. Since the start of the project the community has been expanding already thanks to social media activity, engagement during events and partner and linked third parties reachout.

At the time of writing, SSHOC is expanding its community through LinkedIn (66 connections at the time of writing) and Twitter (367 followers at the time of writing), resulting in a total of 433 users. Other contacts will be acquired through the registration process on SSHOC’s website. Overall acquired contacts are spanning across very different profiles such as:

1. Researchers and scientists in SSH
2. Landmarks and emerging ERICs in SSH
3. Other relevant world class research infrastructures with a European dimension;
4. Research funders and ministries regarding new research priorities to consider;
5. Existing H2020 projects with an impact on the EOSC;
6. Science and data journalists, citizen scientists, open data advocates.

Continuous community monitoring is performed by Trust-IT and it will be circulated regularly to all Consortium Partners.

Samples of additional levers for reaching user communities and other stakeholders

Among SSHOC social media connections a high number of profiles acts as a multiplier and as an influencer generating an elevated resonance among our stakeholders. Our social media communication will leverage on their network of followers to increase the project's visibility.

Below are some of the channels that are following SSHOC's Twitter account at the time of submission the deliverable (March 2019) and that represent relevant numbers in terms of followers in fields that are of interest to SSHOC's community (see table 5).

TABLE 5: SSHOC Twitter followers (March 2019) and possible levers to reach user communities and other stakeholders.

Organisation	Logo ⁴	Twitter account	Stakeholder group	Followers
SciencesPo		@sciencespo	Universities & Research Performing Organisations	105.000
Figshare		@figshare	Private sector & industry players	35.800
KNAW - Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences		@_knav	Universities & Research Performing Organisations	13.900
Recherche SciencesPo		@ScPoResearch	Universities & Research Performing Organisations	13.300
OpenAIRE		@OpenAIRE_eu	Research & e-Infrastructures	10.700
Research Data Alliance		@resdatall	Research & e-Infrastructures	8.847
UKDataService		@UKDataService	Research & e-Infrastructures	8.235
European Social Survey		@ESS_Survey	Research & e-Infrastructures	7.932
LIBEReuropa		@LIBEReuropa	Research Libraries & Archives	5.691
DARIAH-EU		@DARIAHeu	Research & e-Infrastructures	5.587
Open Science MOOC		@OpenScienceMOOC	Private Sector & Industry Players	5.502
Foster Open Science		@fosterscience	Research & e-Infrastructures	5.059

⁴ The logos are subject to copyright and do not fall under the document's creative commons license.

UK Data Archive		@UKDataArchive	Research Libraries & Archives	5.400
Huma-Num		@Huma_Num	Research & e-Infrastructures	4.810
Inist-CNRS		@INIST_CNRS	Universities & Research Performing Organisations	3.254
Europeana Research		@EurResearch	Research Libraries & Archives	2.660
CLARIN ERIC		@CLARINERIC	Research & e-Infrastructures	2.282
CESSDA ERIC		@CESSDA_Data	Research & e-Infrastructures	1.900

4.2 Content-driven approach

The communication and dissemination plan will concentrate its efforts around copywriting and producing engaging, stimulating and impactful content. Our editorial planning will include the regular publication of articles covering partners highlights, EOSC in practice stories, and a news piece to send to EOSC portal editorial board every month.

To tell the story of the SSHOC journey additional inputs will be required from partners, linked third parties, and from the general SSHOC community, as they constitute a fundamental part of this human and social centred story. We will make sure that all the voices in the community are heard and that their events and results are disseminated.

Examples of the content-driven approach for SSHOC

WP2 will produce easy-to-read digests of deliverables for stakeholders, communities, partners, and reviewers so that this journey will be continuously communicated and clear for everybody. These digests will show the work that the project is continuously carrying out over the course of its 40-month duration, the barriers encountered, and the solutions found. Best practices will be easy-accessible from the SSHOC website.

SSHOC pools together Research Infrastructural excellence from the Social Sciences & Humanities Cluster Communities. Efforts have been made to show the project partners who will, over the next 40 months, be building the new cloud-based infrastructure to make data, tools, and training available for scholars in the Social Sciences and Humanities. These first inputs from the partners were gathered in preparation for the Kick-off through the use of an online survey. The gathered information was then used to produce partners highlights slideshow to illustrate the faces and the organisations behind the project. This was ensured by streaming slideshow on screens during the Kick-off event in some of the main areas of the venue, a mean to maximise the impact and to directly involve partners and linked third parties. Partners highlights will be also used in many other ways as they will be included in the communication toolbox, posted on the website homepage as testimonials, used for social media content, and articles.

Highlighting SSHOC partners

"In the SSHOC project, DARIAH-ERIC is leading WP7 and the activities to develop an Open Marketplace, an easy-entry place where humanities scholars will find solutions and resources for the digital aspects of their research. The Open Marketplace will focus on the methodical, dynamic aspects of the research process to enable sharing and re-use not just of resources but workflows and methodologies, to promote Open Methods next to Open Data and Open Source. DARIAH-ERIC and its linked third parties -- OEAW, PSNC and UGOE -- are also involved in WPs 3 and 6".

FIGURE 5: PARTNERS HIGHLIGHTS - DARIAH-EU

WP2 team will be monitoring the development process of the SSHOC Marketplace and give great importance to its role in SSHOC. Every addition or update on the Marketplace will be highlighted and promptly communicated.

SSHOC's content will be made available under the conditions of a Creative Commons open license, in line with the European Commission's approach towards research data which is "as open as possible, as closed as needed". The preferred license for the project's communication output is a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

4.3 Visual identity and branding

A consistent visual identity will be used for all communication and dissemination activities. Templates for external communication and documents will be provided. Presentations templates are already available including on the last page a call to join the SSHOC community and to connect with our main channels.

FIGURE 6: PRESENTATION TEMPLATE LAST PAGE WITH CALL TO ACTION TO JOIN THE SSHOC COMMUNITY.

There will be a final branding alignment across all formats and channels used to reach stakeholders, spanning the Marketplace and integrated news, social media, brochures, banners, posters, and other collaterals.

The logo consists of a blue, orange, and white emblem and the lettering "SSHOC social sciences & humanities open cloud". There is a compact version and an extended version of the logo (see figure 7). SSHOC is the most human-centric cluster in the EOCS and the logo aimed to represent exactly that concept. The two outer semi-circles represent communities and they suggest interconnection. Their sinuous shapes call to mind the double S of Social Sciences while appearing human as well. Another smaller human figure stands at the centre, representing Humanities. The lines touch and intersect, but the overall logo remains an open circuit, to remember that information and science should be open and accessible to the community.

FIGURE 7: COMPACT AND EXTENDED SSHOC LOGO.

Other important parts of SSHOC's visual identity are collaterals, which support the branding of the project. Examples include two heads with bulbs, representing the ideas of research and innovation, and a three-dimensional network, representing the cloud. (Figure 8).

FIGURE 8: EXAMPLE OF THE USE OF COLLATERALS FOR A SSHOC SOCIAL MEDIA BANNER.

In line with Article 38.1.2. of the Grant Agreement the information of EU funding will always be present by a prominently displayed EU emblem and the text suggested in the Grant Agreement: “This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823782”.⁵ Further it will be disclaimed, that the content does not represent the opinion of the European Commission and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

4.4 Step-by-step promotion of events through SSHOC outreach channels

Event promotion, coverage and follow-up is central for SSHOC’s outreach. A perfect example of the promotion of a SSHOC event could be about the Kick-off Meeting coverage as shown in the Figure 9 below:

Pre-event	Opening	Hashtag launch and announcement
<p>Pre-event</p> <p>SSHOpenCloud @SSHOpenCloud</p> <p>The @SSHOpenCloud is about to kick-off! Our first official event is going to be in Utrecht, The Netherlands on March 11-12. Registration is open to all partners, organisations and invites of the #SSHOC Project. Read the details and the agenda here: sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-kic-...</p> <p>5:01 AM - 11 Mar 2019</p> <p>6 Retweets 11 Likes</p>		

⁵ SSHOC Grant Agreement

FIGURE 9: EXAMPLE TWEETS FOR SSHOC EVENTS.

During the two days of SSHOC’s Kick-off event its tweets registered a total of 34.055 impressions. Emphasis was given on the human factor, always showing the speakers and relating them to the partners involved.

To gather questions from the audience and to generate a constant visual flow of tweets during the event, SSHOC’s twitter profile and some relevant hashtags were connected to a Walls.io Social Wall. Questions were then grouped under the #SSHOCquestion hashtag and put to the speakers live (see Figure 10).

FIGURE 10: 2 VIEWS OF THE SSHOC KICKOFF SOCIAL MEDIA WALL.

4.5 Examples of messaging and value proposition

In line with current trends, SSHOC’s social media activities are focused on actionable, goal-oriented, highly-visual, content-rich posts that combine insightful, yet concise text content, hashtags, engaging images and videos. For example, the short post below (Figure 11) focuses on the European Open Science Cloud context SSHOC operates in and its cross-domain liaisons that it already established in this early stage of the project.

FIGURE 11: EXAMPLE TWEET BY THE SSHOC TWITTER CHANNEL.

Some of the targeted messages aim to highlight SSHOC’s presence at events as well as content, such as the short post below (Figure 12).

FIGURE 12: EXAMPLE TWEET BY THE SSHOC TWITTER CHANNEL.

The activities on the various social media channels will also be supported by press releases, such as the first press release on the launch of the SSHOC project. While the simple posts with text and visuals are meant to have an immediate impact in terms of creating interest, press releases deliver great results also for targeting the specialised journalists and other multipliers. The fact of publishing the press release on social platforms such as LinkedIn, populated by a lot of potential stakeholders, is a great advantage as it allows interested readers to find out more by even just having a short look at the article.

An effective press release campaign offers the chance to underline the attributes of SSHOC to anyone who gains interest by reading about it in the shorter posts, and it also involves important SEO benefits, thereby increasing traffic to the website (example: see Figure 13).

FIGURE 13: EXAMPLE OF THE SSHOC WEBPAGE NEWS ITEMS LINKING TO PRESS RELEASES.

4.6 Visibility at Events

Every SSHOC related event, workshop, or webinar will be communicated and posted on the dedicated section of SSHOC’s website and social media channels, covering pre-, during-, and post-event activities.

Collaterals will help in building the SSHOC identity and implementing the Dissemination & Outreach strategy. Branded SSHOC notebooks and pens and a SSHOC official banner are already available and will be brought and exposed at SSHOC related events (examples see figure 14).

FIGURE 14: EXAMPLE OF SSHOC COLLATERALS.

SSHOC related events will be promoted through social media activities and through dedicated campaigns. Prior to the event, we will promote “save the date” posts, publish the event and the agenda on SSHOC’s website, track all links involved in the campaign, formulate dedicated hashtags and create articles, videos, and banners. These events will receive an appropriate follow-up through PPT publication, wrap-up posts, and video interviews from the event.

Events that are directly related to SSHOC as well as those that represent a promotion opportunity for the consortium will be listed in a dedicated event database, shared with all partners and linked third parties. The current event file shows the type of event, the related task, leading participant, communities addressed and the approximate number of participants to be reached, as well as the relevance, place, dates, links and further information (for a compromised version see Table 6).

TABLE 6: LIST OF UPCOMING SSHOC RELATED EVENTS

Event	Date	Organisation	Relevant Communities Addressed
ENVRI FAIR Kick-off Meeting	14 Jan 2019	ENVRI FAIR	Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Universities & Research Performing Organisations; Policy Making Organisations; Research Funding Organisations
PaNOSC Kick-off Meeting	15-16 Jan 2019	PaNOSC	Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Universities & Research Performing Organisations; Policy Making Organisations; Research Funding Organisations
ESCAPE Kick-off Meeting	7-8 Feb 2019	ESCAPE	Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Universities & Research Performing Organisations; Policy Making Organisations; Research Funding Organisations
EURISE Workshop: Software Sustainability within Research Infrastructures	12-13 Mar 2019	CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations; Policy Making Organisations; Research Funding Organisations;
Annual Comparative Survey Design and Implementation Workshop	18-20 Mar 2019	CSDI - Comparative Survey Design and Implementation	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures; Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations;
EOSC-Life Kick-off Meeting	20 Mar 2019	EOSC-Life	Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Universities & Research Performing Organisations; Policy Making Organisations; Research Funding Organisations
EOSC-Hub Week SSHOC Poster Presentation	10-12 Apr 2019	EOSC-Hub	All of SSHOC's stakeholders
Workshop - Services to support FAIR Data Part 1: Prague	12 Apr 2019	OpenAIRE, RDA Europe, FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-hub	Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Private Sector & Industry Players
Workshop - Services to support FAIR Data Part 2: Vienna	24 Apr 2019	OpenAIRE, RDA Europe, FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-hub	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations
European Social Survey International Conference	24-26 Apr 2019	ESS - European Social Survey	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations

DARIAH Annual Event	15-17 May 2019	DARIAH-EU	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations
LIBER Annual Conference and Workshops SSHOC Poster presentation SSHOC Workshop	26-28 Jun 2019	LIBER	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations
European Survey Research Association Conference	15-19 Jul 2019	ESRA - European Survey Research Association	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations
IC2S2 - International Conference in Computational Social Science	17-20 Jul 2019	IC2S2	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations
Workshop - Services to support FAIR Data Part 3: Porto	17 Sep 2019	OpenAIRE, RDA Europe, FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-hub	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations; Policy Making Organisations; Private Sector & Industry players
CLARIN Annual Conference	30 Sep - 2 Oct 2019	CLARIN ERIC	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations
EOSC meeting during RDA Plenary 13	23-25 Oct 2019	RDA	Researchers; Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters); Research Libraries & Archives; Universities & Research Performing Organisations; Policy Making Organisations; Research Funding Organisations

4.7 Monitoring the impact

WP2 will set up a Monitoring Service tailored to SSHOC to measure the impact achieved by the communication activities carried out. We will set up a shared dashboard, that will visually render all the data from our communications and online activities for a continuous and easy monitoring of KPIs. Necessary adjustments will be made during the course of the project. Alerts about the SSHOC community will be activated to keep track of the buzz around the project.

A sample dashboard that will be set-up for SSHOC is reported in the figure below (Figure 15):

FIGURE 15: EXAMPLE OF MONITORING DASHBOARD FROM EOSC-HUB THAT WILL BE SET-UP FOR SSHOC.

Flash reports

Reports involving social media engagement and outreach will also be delivered internally to partners and to the project management. Starting from M4, a recap mail should be sent monthly providing insights on the impact generated by SSHOC's online activities and also including visual references to SSHOC's monitoring dashboard and to the gathered data.

5. Conclusion

The present document is the basis for all Dissemination and Outreach activities to be carried out in SSHOC over the project's lifetime. The main conclusions are:

- The “SSHOC Overall Communication and Outreach Plan” is tightly linked to the project results and therefore is to be considered as a living document: It will be up to the “Communication, Dissemination and Impact” work package to timely update it whenever necessary.
- WP2 activities in the first three months of the project have been conducted with good coordination and produced tangible results, including completion of project branding, launch of the new website, visibility at events and production of a number of collaterals.
- A first timeline for the period M4-M12 has been developed and it will be followed as part of WP2 as well as an overview from M4-M40 for SSHOC.
- All Consortium partners have shown good alignment and high commitment in development and implementation of the present plan.

6. References

SSHOC Grant Agreement

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/open-innovation-open-science-open-world-vision-europe>

OSPP-REC – DRAFT recommendations of the Open Science Policy Platform

Annex I – Timelines M1-M6

An effective communication and dissemination strategy follows a rigorous weekly and monthly timeline, which is closely monitored. An example of a monthly timeline that has been created for the project Kick-off meeting is reported below (figures 16 and 17) and it will be constantly adjourned.

FIGURE 1: SSHOC TIMELINE: JANUARY-MARCH

FIGURE 2: SSHOC TIMELINE: APRIL-JUNE